

AN ASYMPTOTIC SOLUTION TO DENSITY DISTRIBUTION OF GRADED CELLULAR MATERIALS WITH A CONSTANT IMPACT LOAD

B.X. Chang^{1,2}, Z. J. Zheng^{1*}, K. Zhao¹ and J. L. Yu¹

¹ CAS Key Laboratory of Mechanical Behavior and Design Materials, Department of Modern Mechanics, University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei 230027, China

² State Key Laboratory for Strength and Vibration of Mechanical Structures, School of Aerospace, Xi'an Jiaotong University, Xi'an 710049, China

*zjzheng@ustc.edu.cn, <http://staff.ustc.edu.cn/~zjzheng/>

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ABSTRACT

A simplified model for the density design of graded cellular materials has been proposed with a dimensionless differential equation when the impact force is considered to be constant. An asymptotic solution to the governing equation is obtained by applying the series method. The cell-based finite element (FE) models of graded cellular materials are constructed by applying the varying cell-size distribution method with 3D Voronoi technology. The theoretical design is verified by using finite element software ABAQUS/Explicit. The results show that the asymptotic solution of the simplified model is valid for the crashworthiness design requirement of graded cellular materials. The proposed crashworthiness design method is of instructive significance in controlling the energy absorption and impact process.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cellular materials have novel properties, such as high porosity and lightweight, and have been extensively used for the crashworthiness design of structures in the automotive, railway and aeronautical industries [1-3]. Under dynamic impact situation, the stresses at the impact end and at the support end of a cellular specimen could be very different, and the deformation is localized at the impact end[4]. These special mechanical behaviors of cellular materials are beneficial to improve the crashworthiness of structures. The macroscopic mechanical behaviors of cellular materials are related to many properties, such as microscopic heterogeneities of cell shape, size and wall thickness [5-7]. The mechanical responses of graded cellular materials are very sensitive to their relative density distribution and the effect of meso-structures can be different [5]. For different impact situations, the crashworthiness requirements of structures also need to be considered from different perspectives and may be realized with the design of density gradients of cellular materials.

The dynamic mechanical responses of graded cellular material with a given density distribution have been extensively investigated [8-10], but few work has been carried out to understand the crashworthiness design principle of graded cellular materials. Based on a nonlinear plastic shock wave model, Yang et al. [11] first proposed a design strategy for determining the density distribution of cellular materials to meet the crashworthiness requirement of protecting a mass when impinging a graded cellular rod with an initial impact velocity. This backward crashworthiness design method opens up a new idea of obtaining a controllable impact force with using graded cellular materials. Unfortunately, the differential equation to determine the density distribution of cellular material can not present an explicit solution. A fourth-order Runge-Kutta scheme has been used by Yang et al. [11] to solve the differential equation to obtain numerical solutions for the crashworthiness requirements of linear increasing force, constant force and linear decreasing force. Recently, Chang et al. [12] proposed an asymptotic solution to the density distribution of graded honeycomb material for the case of constant impact force and it has been verified by 2D cell-based finite element model. Subsequently, Chang et al.[13] also proposed an asymptotic solution for the case of using closed-cell foam. Different types of cellular materials usually have different relations between material parameters (initial crush

stress and strain hardening parameter) and relative density. The asymptotic solution for Voronoi honeycombs is not valid to guide design for closed-cell foam.

This study aims to obtain an asymptotic solution to guide the backward design of different meso-configurations cellular materials (such as honeycomb and closed-cell foam). An asymptotic solution based on the design strategy is obtained in Section 2. Specimens with some specific gradient densities are constructed by using the 3D Voronoi technique also in Section 2. The effectiveness of the asymptotic solution is verified in Section 3. Conclusions are given in Section 4.

2 THEORETICAL AND NUMERICAL MODELS

2.1 Problem description

Figure 1: Schematic diagram for the single shock front model of graded cellular rod ^[12]

We consider a static graded cellular rod with cross-sectional area A_0 impinged by an object with mass M and an initial impact velocity V_0 , as illustrated in Figure 1. The object is considered to be protected, which requires the impact force $F(t)$ exerted on the object should be less than the limit that the object can be withstand. In this study, the impact force $F(t)$ is taken to be a constant F_0 during impacting. The density distribution of graded cellular rod should be specially designed according to the crashworthiness requirements and the mechanical properties of cellular materials. Although the rate-independent, rigid-perfectly plastic-locking (R-PP-L) has been extensively used to characterize the stress-strain features of three distinctive stages of cellular materials under compression, Zheng et al.[15] proposed a more accurate stress-strain relation, namely a rate-independent, rigid-plastic-hardening (R-PH) idealization, which is expressed as

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 + \frac{C\varepsilon}{(1-\varepsilon)^2}, \quad (1)$$

where σ_0 and C are the initial crush stress and the strain hardening parameter, respectively.

Many researches have shown that the mechanical behavior of cellular materials under quasi-static loading is relative to the density [2, 11, 14]. Based on the R-PH material model, the initial crush stress σ_0 and the strain hardening parameter C were found to be related to the relative density ρ of cellular materials in power-law fashions [11, 14]

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_0(\rho) = s_0\rho^{n_1} \\ C(\rho) = C_0\rho^{n_2} \end{cases}, \quad (2)$$

where $s_0 = k_1\sigma_{ys}$, $C_0 = k_2\sigma_{ys}$, σ_{ys} is the yield stress of the cell-wall material, k_1 , n_1 , k_2 and n_2 are fitting coefficients. For different meso-configurations, the exponents could be very difference. From the previous studies, we can have: $k_1 = 0.439$, $n_1 = 2$, $k_2 = 0.127$ and $n_2 = 2$ for Voronoi honeycomb [14]; $k_1 = 0.885$, $n_1 = 1.37$, $k_2 = 0.115$ and $n_2 = 1.5$ for closed-cell foam [11].

During the impacting, the localization of deformation can be observed at the proximal end, when the graded cellular rod which the relative density only increases monotonic along the loading direction was impacted by a mass with a relatively high velocity. A compressive shock front travels from the proximal end to the distal end of the graded cellular metal rod. The shock-front speed is given by $\dot{\Phi}(t)$,

where $\Phi(t)$ is the shock-front location in terms of the impact time t . The relative density of the current location of the shock front is $\rho(\Phi(t))$. The stress, particle velocity and strain behind the shock front are $\{\sigma_B(t), v(t), \varepsilon_B(t)\}$ and ahead of the shock front are $\{\sigma_0(\rho(\Phi(t))), 0, 0\}$, in which $v(t)$ is the mass impact velocity. The rigid mass moves with the densification portion of the cellular rod until the impact velocity of the mass reduces to zero. According to the Newton's motion law, the acceleration of the object is expressed as

$$\frac{dv(t)}{dt} = -\frac{F_0}{M} = -\frac{\sigma_B(t)}{m + \rho_s \int_0^{\Phi(t)} \rho(X) dX}, \quad (3)$$

where m is the mass per unit section area.

According to the shock wave theory, the mass and momentum conservation conditions across the shock front are expressed as

$$\begin{cases} v(t) - 0 = \dot{\Phi}(t)(\varepsilon_B(t) - 0) \\ \sigma_B(t) - \sigma_0(\rho) = \rho_s \rho \dot{\Phi}(t)(v(t) - 0) \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

where ρ_s is the density of the cell-wall material. Based on the R-PH material model [15], the relation between the shock-front speed and the impact velocity can be written as

$$\dot{\Phi}(t) = v(t) + c(\rho), \quad (5)$$

where $c = (C/\rho_s \rho)^{1/2}$ is the dynamic material parameter. From Eq. (2), the dynamic material parameter can be rewritten as $c(\rho) = c_0 \rho^\lambda$, where $c_0 = \sqrt{C_0 / \rho_s}$ and $\lambda = (n_2 - 1)/2$. By combining Eq. (4) and Eq. (5), the shock stress σ_B can be given by

$$\sigma_B(t) = \sigma_0(\rho) + \rho_s \rho v(t)(v(t) + c(\rho)). \quad (6)$$

Combining Eq. (3), Eq. (5) and Eq. (6) leads to

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dv(t)}{dt} = -\frac{\sigma_0(\rho) + \rho_s \rho v(t)(v(t) + c(\rho))}{m + \rho_s \int_0^{\Phi(t)} \rho(X) dX} \\ \frac{d\Phi(t)}{dt} = v(t) + c(\rho) \end{cases}. \quad (7)$$

The initial crush stress σ_0 and the strain hardening parameter C are related to the relative density, as presented in Eq. (2). For a specified relative density distribution of a graded cellular rod, the dynamic mechanical behavior can be determined from Eq. (7).

2.2 Backward design theory

In this study, a simplified model of the design strategy presented by Yang et al. [11] meeting the requirements of crashworthiness to keep a constant impact force can be simplified as

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\rho}{dt} = \frac{a_0 \rho_s \rho (3v + 2c(\rho))}{\sigma'_0(\rho) + \rho_s v^2 + \rho_s v(c(\rho) + \rho c'(\rho))} \\ \frac{d\Phi}{dt} = v + c(\rho) \\ \frac{dv}{dt} = -a_0 \end{cases}, \quad (8)$$

where $a_0 = F_0/M$ is the deceleration of the object, Φ is the location of shock front, and the apostrophe stands for the derivative with respect to ρ .

In order to obtain an asymptotic solution, we define four characteristic parameters of the system, including the characteristic length L_0 , the characteristic time T_0 , the characteristic relative density ρ_0 and the characteristic velocity V_0 . The characteristic time T_0 is the impact duration derived from the momentum theorem, i.e. $FT_0 = MV_0$ and the characteristic length L_0 is determined from $L_0 = V_0 T_0$. The initial conditions are $v(0) = V_0$, $\Phi(0) = 0$, $\rho(\Phi(0)) = \rho_0$, where the initial relative density ρ_0 is determined from $\sigma_0(\rho_0) + \rho_s \rho_0 V_0 (V_0 + c(\rho_0)) = F_0/A_0$. The dimensionless form of Eq. (8) is given by

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\bar{\rho}}{d\bar{\Phi}} = \frac{\bar{\rho}(3\bar{v} + 2\bar{c}_0\bar{\rho}^\lambda)}{(n_1\bar{s}_0\bar{\rho}^{n_1-1} + \bar{v}^2 + \bar{v}\bar{c}_0\bar{\rho}^\lambda(1+\lambda))(\bar{v} + \bar{c}_0\bar{\rho}^\lambda)} \\ \frac{d\bar{v}}{d\bar{\Phi}} = -(\bar{v} + \bar{c}_0\bar{\rho}^\lambda)^{-1} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where $\bar{\rho} = \rho / \rho_0$, $\bar{v} = v / V_0$, $\bar{t} = t / T_0$, $\bar{\Phi} = \Phi / L_0$, $\bar{v} = 1 - \bar{t}$, $\bar{s}_0 = s_0 \rho_0^{n_1-1} / (\rho_s V_0^2)$ and $\bar{c}_0 = c_0 \rho_0^\lambda / V_0$.

We apply a series expansion method to solve Eq. (9) and obtain an asymptotic solution

$$\begin{cases} \bar{\rho}(\bar{\Phi}) = 1 + a_1\bar{\Phi} + a_2\bar{\Phi}^2 + O(\bar{\Phi}^3) \\ \bar{v}(\bar{\Phi}) = 1 + b_1\bar{\Phi} + b_2\bar{\Phi}^2 + O(\bar{\Phi}^3) \end{cases}, \quad (10)$$

with the first-order asymptotic coefficients (a_1, b_1) and the second-order asymptotic coefficients (a_2, b_2)

$$\begin{cases} a_1 = \frac{3 + 2\bar{c}_0}{(1 + \bar{c}_0)(1 + n_1\bar{s}_0 + (1 + \lambda)\bar{c}_0)} \\ b_1 = -\frac{1}{1 + \bar{c}_0} \end{cases}, \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{cases} a_2 = \frac{b_1^2\bar{c}_0 + \lambda a_1^2\bar{c}_0(1 + \lambda)(1 + \bar{c}_0) + n_1 a_1^2 \bar{s}_0 (n_1 - 1)(1 + \bar{c}_0) + a_1 b_1 (\lambda \bar{c}_0^2 + (1 + \bar{c}_0)(5 + 3\bar{c}_0))}{2(1 + \bar{c}_0)(1 + n_1\bar{s}_0 + (1 + \lambda)\bar{c}_0)} \\ b_2 = -\frac{b_1(b_1 + \lambda a_1\bar{c}_0)}{2(1 + \bar{c}_0)} \end{cases}. \quad (12)$$

The length of graded cellular rod obtained based on the first-order approximate solution when the impact velocity equals zero is given by $L_{\text{sample}_1} = -L_0/b_1$, and the length of graded cellular rod obtained based on the second-order approximate solution is given by $L_{\text{sample}_2} = -(b_1 + \sqrt{b_1^2 - 4b_2})L_0/2b_2$.

2.3 Cell-based finite element model

Cell-based finite element (FE) models are employed to verify the asymptotic solution of the relative density distribution, see Figure 2. Numerical simulations are carried out by using ABAQUS/Explicit code. Specimens with gradient density distribution are constructed by using the 3D Voronoi technique, see Ref. [11] for details. The cell irregularity is 0.4. The matrix material of graded cellular samples is assumed to be rate-independent, elastic-perfectly plastic with density $\rho_s = 2700 \text{ kg/m}^3$, Young's modulus $E_s = 69 \text{ GPa}$, Poisson's ratio $\nu_s = 0.3$, and yield stress $\sigma_{ys} = 165 \text{ MPa}$. The characteristic size of shell elements is set to be about 0.3 mm, which has been selected for a mesh sensitivity study [15]. The matrix materials are modeled by shell elements of type S4R. General contact with a friction coefficient of 0.02 is applied to all possible contacts during crushing. The cross section A_0 of samples has a size of $30 \times 30 \text{ mm}^2$. The impact object has been replaced by a rigid plate with mass M with initial impact velocity V_0 . The distal end of samples is in contact with another rigid plate which is completely fixed.

Figure 2: Illustration of a specimen of density-graded cellular structure using a 3D Voronoi model.

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The relative density distributions

In this study, we consider the impact situation and crashworthiness requirement that the mass of the impact object M is 50g, the initial impact velocity V_0 is 100 m/s, the impact force F_0 is 7.5 kN. The initial relative density ρ_0 is 0.851. And, we have $\bar{c}_0 = 0.453$ and $\bar{s}_0 = 2.17$, thus Eq. (12) gives $a_1 = 0.592$, $a_2 = 0.222$, $b_1 = -0.688$ and $b_2 = -0.143$. The length of the specimen designed with the first-order approximate solution is 96.9 mm, and that of second-order approximate solution is 78.0 mm.

The asymptotic solutions with different order approximations and the exact solution of the relative density distributions are presented in Figure 3. The exact solution is obtained numerically with a fourth-order Runge-Kutta scheme. The first-order approximate solution is linearly close to the exact solution. The second-order approximate solution is much close to the exact solution. The samples' lengths of the two approximate solutions are larger than that of the exact solution.

Figure 3: Relative density distributions for the initial impact velocity $V_0 = 100$ m/s

3.2 Deformation patterns from cell-based finite element models

Cell-based FE models for two approximate solutions are constructed by the varying cell-size distribution method based on Voronoi technology. In the situation of the initial impact velocity $V_0=100$ m/s, the deformation evolution of graded cellular rods are presented in Figure 4. The middle cross-sections perpendicular to the X-axis of cell-based FE models are shown. Based on the R-PH shock model, the deformation development for the FE models corresponding to the first-order approximate solution and the second-order approximate solution are shown in Figure 4 (a) and (b). Throughout the impact process, the deformation localization occurs at the impact end. The crushing zone moves to the distal end with the passage of time in only one direction.

Figure 4: Diagrams of the deformation patterns for a middle cross-section perpendicular to the X -axis of cell-based FE models: (a) an FE model corresponding to the first-order approximate solution; (b) an FE model corresponding to the second-order approximate solution;

3.3 Results of cell-based finite element models

Verification investigations are carried out by using cell-based FE models. The impact force history curves of different design samples are plotted in Figure 5. The data fluctuations exist in the results of FE calculation. The reasons are: a) in the initial contact phase, penalty function contact algorithm between the impact rigid plate and the graded cellular rod can lead to the severe data fluctuation; b) the higher frequency fluctuation in the later period is caused by the propagation of elastic waves and interaction inside cell wall; c) the low frequency and large amplitude fluctuations are caused by the collapse of cells. The impact force history curve obtained from the cell-based FE model with using the second-order approximate solution is much close to the design goal. The design using the first-order approximate solution is not accurate enough, but in fact it is not so bad. To design a less length of graded cellular rod, it is recommended to use the second-order approximate solution. The self-consistency of asymptotic solutions is verified.

The impact velocity evolutions of the impact object obtained from cell-based FE models are shown in Figure 6. The impact duration is determined from the time when the impact velocity reduces to zero. The impact duration for the FE models corresponding to the first-order approximate solution, the second-order approximate solution and the exact solution are 0.657ms, 0.622ms and 0.615ms, which are less than the theoretical prediction value (0.667ms). It means that the average accelerations are higher than the design objective. In Figure 5, we can also see that the results of finite element calculation are slightly higher than the design objective value. The possible reason is that the

backward design does not consider the impact loading rate sensitivity of cellular materials. Under the quasi-static and dynamic loadings, the mechanical responses of cellular material are very different. The stress-strain curve under dynamic loading shows a higher initial crush stress and a larger densification strain [15]. The strain rate sensitivity of the initial crush stress of cellular materials was reported by Ding et al.[16] and Wang et al.[17]. Therefore, the influence of the impact loading rate sensitivity of the cellular material may be considered in the later study to improve the accuracy of the design.

Figure 5: Comparison of impact force history curves obtained from cell-based FE models

Figure 6: The impact velocity evolutions of the impact object obtained from cell-based FE models

4 CONCLUSIONS

Based on a nonlinear plastic shock model, a density design strategy of graded cellular material was further developed. A simplified model was proposed with a dimensionless differential equation when the impact force is considered to be constant. An asymptotic solution to the density design is obtained by applying the series expansion method. A case study shows that the first-order approximate solution is linearly close to the exact solution obtained numerically with a fourth-order Runge-Kutta scheme, and the second-order approximate solution is very close to the exact solution. The samples' lengths of the two approximate solutions are larger than that of the exact solution. Cell-based FE models are employed to verify the design strategy. The impact force history curve obtained from the cell-based FE model with using the second-order approximate solution is much close to the design goal. The design using the first-order approximate solution is not accurate enough, but in fact it is not so bad. It's shown that the asymptotic solution can be a good guide for the density gradient design of closed-cell foam materials to meet the design goals of crashworthiness. In further study, the impact loading rate may be considered to improve the accuracy of the design.

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